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Educating For Value Reorientation Through University Teacher Education For Sustainable Transformation In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined educating for value reorientation through university teacher education for sustainable transformation in Nigeria. The concept of value reorientation, teacher education and sustainable transformation were discussed briefly. Some process-steps required for value reorientation were itemized, how to initiate value reorientation in teacher education explained as well as the outcome of value reorientation in the society highlighted. Also, the challenges to value reorientation for sustainable transformation were mentioned and how to curb such challenges were stated. It was then concluded that the best place to begin value reorientation for sustainable transformation would be the classroom. The following suggestions were given to support the study, that the university management should ensure that only corruption free persons are given appointive positions to begin value reorientation in the system, teacher educators should model what they teach their students in their worklife and lifestyle for immediate result in value reorientation, teacher trainees should emulate good character and jettison the negative ones on display by their lecturers in order to have a better next generation etc.

Keywords: Value reorientation, teacher education, sustainable transformation

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of exposing a learner to opportunities to draw out of him potentials possessed by the individual towards personal and societal development. Amadiha and Akor (2018) had defined education as a process by which children and young adults develop abilities, attitudes and any other behavior which is of positive value towards bringing about change in the society. This particular definition of education is limited as it alienated older people in the society who also are entitled to their education. Ahmed and Saidu (2014) see education as a tool used in instilling the right way of life and value into young people, this again is limited. But Ada (2012) says that education is an instrument used for self-development and for the development of the society as the person opens up inherent potentials to usage. Kalagbor (2023) says that education as a variable facilitates knowledge and it is sustained in a technologically advancing world. This particular definition captured education in the context of present realities of life. Therefore, education could be conceived as a facilitator of personal engineering towards unleashing the potentials, abilities, knowledge, skills, values and attitudes required to make for the constant development of the persons and the society at large. The foregoing

ideation presents education as a process, thus, procedural, step-step or stage by stage, hence, an act. So, it is the act of education that is referred to as educating when it is a done thing or what is in practice presently.

According to Amemtaan (2024) the concept of educating is presented as a verb in action and viewed as an act or engagement in education; a process of guiding someone in the learning process. Therefore, educating could mean guiding, teaching, provision of learning experience to the learner with the intent of making another to maximize in-built capacity. This process ensures that the learner maximizes every opportunity available to draw out potentials yet untapped and as well as better on tapped knowledge, skills, attitudes and values in order to be a better citizen. Based on the assertion of the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2016) education takes place at various levels in Nigeria to include early childhood education, basic education (Primary and Junior Secondary School), mass literacy, adult education and non-formal education, and tertiary education. Though, usually in order to make it simple, it is broken into Basic, Secondary and Tertiary education were university education falls.

University is a place where people engage in higher level of learning. Akor (2021) says it is an institution of higher level of learning where students obtain degrees and certificates. This presents university education as an arm of tertiary education practice. Its major pursuits are:

- i. Intensifying and diversifying its programme for the development of high level manpower within the context of the needs of the nation
- ii. Making all students as part of a general programme of all round improvement in the university education to offer general study courses such as history of ideas, philosophy of knowledge and nationalism (FRN, 2016).

Thus, the university houses many other aspects of education based on its stated functions above among which is the teacher education. Nonetheless, the foregoing presentation paints the university as a place equipped with the responsibility for reorientation considering all it is expected to perform.

Re-orientation is an act towards relearning or unlearning what was perceived as the right knowledge, skills, attitudes and value for the purpose of change and advancement. This conveys that reorientation is aimed towards a change that is required for effectiveness or higher level of effectiveness or even for greater degree of efficiency. Thus, value reorientation connotes a change in value system, believe system and/or even attitudes shown in response to situations, such that depict the character and acceptable personality of a person or a people. Oluwagbohumin (2017) describes reorientation as a pattern of changing the way things were previously done and adopting or adapting the old pattern to suite the present need and demand. So, for reorientation to take place, it means that there exist an orientation which does not conform to what would help such a society to make progress, thus, the need for reorientation and in most cases, when reorientation takes place a shift in value system occurs. Value system is an operational practice that is held at a high esteem or standard. It represents what is perceived as right or the most appropriate way of doing or acting in a particular situation.

Value reorientation as described above could results from a change in value because of its decayed status or its inability to further produce results based on what the society used to experience and what it now experiences. Anzene (2014) says that because the Nigerian society has been affected greatly by value and moral decadence, the fulcrum of the educational system seem not to be firm enough to carry it any more. For instance, it was a taboo in the past for family members to engage in activities that generated illegal wealth, like use of a family member for ritual to become wealthy but now, it is common sight among the Nigerian people to use family members for ritual without a second thought. Thus, in this light, Oluwagbohumin (2017) sees value reorientation as a process of trying to maintain status quo in the value system of the society that has stood the test of time and change those ones that have no value to add to societal growth and development anymore, so, it becomes imperative to shift stand on them in order to return to where the society has drifted from or to adopt/ adapt to a newer value system that holds a greater level of advantages.

On this ground, value could be viewed as moral or character traits that represent someone or a people's belief system as earlier mentioned. It is the moral or character standing of a person or a people. It is said to be the standards and guides to a people's action or behaviour. Olaogun (2012) says it determines what someone believes as right or wrong. Values could also be seen as traits and qualities that are considered worthwhile, given the greatest priorities in driving a person's life choices and decision and of course the entire life

(Ugodulunwa & Balogun, 2007). While Nduka-Ozo (2016) says it is the rules and regulations, right attitude towards things and others on how to regulate self. All these points to the fact that the society is dynamic and open to changes regularly including change in values, thus, the need for value reorientation and because teacher education is a type of education which is given to training change by agents, it becomes a suitable point of departure when it comes to a discourse of this nature.

Teacher education is the practice of preparing teachers to take up the responsibility of training teachers for the future. Ikpeme and Idakwo (2021) say that teacher education is a procedural approach designed to educate prospective teachers in knowledge, behaviours, skills and attitudes to do their job in the future. This could be perceived as a means of making ready in knowledge, skills and other characteristics that makes a person fit to be called a teacher. A point that reaffirmed the definition of teacher education given by Akor and Agbo (2021) as a process of equipping teacher trainees with desirable knowledge and skills they would need to be teachers in the future society. This is so in that a teacher is usually not prepared for today but in waiting for tomorrow in terms of teaching skills, pedagogical skills and professional skills to be adjudged to be fully ready for the responsibility of teaching without which the idea of sustainability becomes elusive due to poor or inadequate curriculum practice.

Sustainability has to do with the use of available resources for today's needs while bearing its place for tomorrow's need in mind. That is, using scarce resources to meet today's needs yet, ensuring that there is left over for tomorrow's use. Akor, Umor and Pepple (2023) say that sustainability is a concept found in the domain of conservation yet has found relevance when it comes to managing resources that are short in supply for use now for use in the future. Akor and Ochijenu (2024) describe sustainability as the utilization of available resources for today's needs but conserving some for tomorrow's use. Thus, sustainability encourages teachers through the curriculum they have been experienced to pursue the desired transformation needed especially because of their being part of the past society and because teachers in training today are for tomorrow's business of teaching, then, they fit in well here. This is in line with (FRN, 2016) which gave one of the goals of teacher education as 'to provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and make them adaptable to changing situations. This goal makes it intentional for the teacher education process to be at the core of being a transformation agent for the society.

Transformation is a concept tilted towards social change. This kind of change happens incrementally and takes different forms. It is a deep, sustained and systematic change required to redirect the development of the society in a desired direction. Thus, it is a change process that occurs due to processes put in place. Singha (2024) says it is an extensive and pronounced change seen in arrangement or structure of a society. It is further said that it could take any of these forms-conventional, principle, technological, cultural or political leading to significant and known changes that are quantifiable. Therefore, when a society is yearning for adequate change, it must first begin from her teacher education practice considering that 'no nation can rise above the quality of her teachers' (FRN, 2016). Being that the highest level of training given and received is at the university, it would be good to peep into what goes on there.

University education is a set up aimed at producing people who are self-reliant and adaptable to changing societal dynamics. It is a place to gain higher level of knowledge and acquire skills needed to survive in the society and perhaps become a useful member of the society (Akor, 2021). The pursuit so intended would be achievable if there is value re-orientation and present observation by the researchers indicates that the current university students tend to be chasing the laid out intention for the university but are rather involved in hook-up, yahoo-yahoo, money for marks syndrome, sex for mark challenge, kidnapping antics and practice, and quick rich quick syndrome as driven by the lifestyle of the affluent in the society. However, the drive for value reorientation and transformation can only be sustainable when the major tool which is a strong teacher education process is applied especially because of the multiplier effect potential that it holds in the society. Therefore reason for study educating for value reorientation through university teacher education for sustainable transformation in Nigeria.

Value Reorientation

Value reorientation could be viewed as a process of change in attitude towards ideas identified as wrong behavior or thought. Value then could be seen as standardized behavior by which a person or a group of persons live; this means, that value guides the way a person or a people act in a given situation, determining

the quality of identifiable behavior exhibited at any given period in time. So, value is perceived as the initiator of the right, good, something of worth, beauty, wrong, morality among others (Oluwagbohunmi, 2013). Therefore, the process of changing an idea on a particular attitude or behavior to acting in another way is what is called value reorientation. For instance, when Nigeria as a nation was described as fantastically corrupt by the then British Prime Minister (David Cameron), it led the then Minister of Information in Nigeria (Late Professor Dora Akunyili) to disagree with such a label but rather asked for change through the slogan ‘Great people, great nation’. This idea began to bring in the desired effect of the world gradually viewing Nigerians in a different light as the change began to happen even in several diaspora relationships that Nigeria and Nigerians had. But much more importantly was the fact that there began a wave of reorientation in the Nigerian society which made the world to begin to viewing us in a different light.

Beyond the fact of corruption bedeviling the nation, other areas where there is need for value reorientation may include areas like respect for elders, honesty, dignity, cooperation, self-control, delayed gratification, morality, truthfulness, value for social justice, right judgement among others (Omenma & Onuoha, 2021). However, Magaji (2014) had proffered solutions that if Nigerians could develop these features it would mitigate the effect of the above mentioned issues that have made the nation gone down in revered value system, so what to do is to imbibe: competence building, kindness display, fair judgement, courage, acceptance, loyalty, patriotism, dependability etc. Others that Ikonne (2012) mentioned other things that could boost value system rejuvenation as trustworthiness, integrity, selflessness, discipline, orderliness, management for sustenance etc. These features would not just happen to people but needs to be taught to them through the school as a fast means of reaching a greater number of persons with a multiplier effect of the process of conducting the reorientation process to reach a wide space and members of the society who are needed for the change to reflect and to begin, it would just suffice that teacher education serve as the starting point, that is, based on the fact that (FRN, 2016) has it that ‘no nation can rise above her teachers’, therefore, training teachers in this light to be able to teach others is key to achieving any progress in the desired direction.

Teacher Education

Teacher education has to do with the process of preparing teachers for the future job that is ahead of them. Nwadiokwu (2021) viewed teacher education as the education process meant to develop people with the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed for their effectiveness and efficiency at work. This arguably points to the fact that if reorientation and changes would take place in the life of a learner, such should possess the requisite ability to be able to drive what is expected in the life and behavior of the child that would be taught by the individual, thus, teacher education is the central point of departure towards achieving any form of change or value reorientation that may be needed in the society, hence, it should be where the reorientation process begin from. Some of the process steps itemized that could drive value reorientation may be as follows:

1. Rebranding of teacher education programme
2. Positive perception of the teaching profession
3. Quality assurance in teacher education
4. Stable government policies to strengthen teacher education
5. Engagement in continuous review of the teacher education standard guideline to suit the need of the society.
6. Alignment of classroom experience of the learner to daily living
7. Put means in place to reduce the challenges of becoming trainee by chance and force among the students admitted to study education courses (Nwadiokwu, 2021; Nwadiokwu, 2021; Ikpeme & Idakwo, 2021; Amadioha & Akor, 2021).

These steps and more outlined above when properly worked on have the tendency of changing the narrative about teacher education. However, talk is cheap, thus, action is required for the process of achieving the desired value reorientation that can lead to transformation such that is sustainable.

Sustainable Transformation

Sustainable transformation could be viewed as such change that is enduring, standing the test of time and capable of bringing positive vibe into the life and living of the society. Sancak (2023) see sustainable transformation as basic, wide rearrangement using technology, economics and social views to create a shift in paradigm. The idea presented here of sustainable transformation could be inferred as that kind of change

brought about with negligible or no negative effect on the present and the future in terms of available resources required to carry it out. Therefore, it can be deduced that it is possible to initiate and effect transformation process without it causing damage to what is obtainable now and in the future. Thus, the idea of value reorientation through teacher education is possible to engender sustainable transformation without affecting the future negatively.

How to Initiate Value Reorientation in Teacher Education for Sustainable Transformation

Value reorientation is a process that brings about change and because the society is dynamic, then, such reorientation process would require dynamism. So, these steps would be needed:

1. Use of Shared Idea: Authorities in the various fields of teacher education who would drive value reorientation for sustainable transformation should encourage shared ideas among themselves as this is capable of encouraging them to relate the dynamic information based on the society they live in for sustainable transformation (Amadioha & Akor, 2021).
2. Transparency and Accountability: People saddled with responsibility of managing public trust should do well to show adequate stewardship in their conduct and transaction with the way they manages resources available in the society. This would make people to believe them and emulate their character for future dealings (Jamaica & Aleru, 2024).
3. Show of Competency: Teacher educators are expected to display outright competence in the way they operate in activities leading to sustainable transformation as whatever they do is being observed to be emulated or jettisoned. Thus, carefulness is required in the behaviour of the educators towards ensuring quality assurance, discipline, competence and others. (Allison & Dickay, 2021).
4. Government Effort: The government should put in every effort in ensuring that the process of value reorientation through financing and supervision for adequate implementation be adequately managed through hands on provision and removal of bottlenecks that could hamper the process as well as encouraging regular report and follow-up on such reports (Akor & Okonny, 2022).
5. Encouragement of Creativity: The government and education stakeholders should be ready and willing to reward creative efforts made by both students and teacher educators towards ensuring that there is value reorientation in the society. This would go a long way in encouraging sustainable transformation as desired (Udu, Kelechi-Ejike & Amah, 2022).

Outcome of Value Reorientation for Sustainable Transformation Through Teacher Education

1. Multiple positive effects in personal, organizational and societal transformation.
2. High level of motivation for participation and volunteerism in sustainable transformation efforts
3. Long term output of sustainable transformation in value system and belief that is generic in nature.
4. Noticeable application of practical values that displays evidence of change among the populace.
5. Opportunity for development of result oriented skills not being pursued but arising from value reorientation.

Challenges to Value Reorientation for Sustainable Transformation Through Teacher Education

Some factors remain the reasons so many societies are not able to imbibe value reorientation to forge ahead in the pursuit of sustainable transformation. These may include:

1. Endemic corruption.
2. Beaurucratic bottlenecks.
3. Acceptance of unsolicited gifts for marks and grades.
4. Lack of commensurate punishment for fraudulent activities.
5. Lack of cooperation to fight derailment tendencies.
6. Selection of those with negative character into offices.
7. Inability to appropriate results of research to make changes happen etc (Amadioha & Akor, 2020; Chan, 2018).

How to Deal With Challenges Facing Value Reorientation for Sustainable Transformation Through Teacher Education

Some probable steps to take in dealing with the challenges mentioned above and more may include:

- a. Regular review of the curriculum to capture areas in need of value reorientation process.
- b. Regular training and retraining programmes through conferences, workshops and seminar for teacher educators to keep hands on deck.
- c. Skills acquisition that would help up-skilling for those who are not in school should be organized regularly through village and community advocacy programmes
- d. Those who are caught in corrupt practices should be delivered to face the justice system.
- e. Measures should be put in place to determine true accountability and transparency in service delivery in established institutions etc.

CONCLUSION

Based on this study, conclusion could be drawn that the best place to start value reorientation would be the classrooms and that university students in teacher education process could be used as the spanning line for value reorientation in the society such that holds sustainable transformation. Considering some of the steps that include the use of curriculum through its regular review to match the need and dynamism of the society, some menace like immediate gratification, gifts in exchange for passes, yahoo-yahoo tendencies arising from get rich quick syndrome that has now overwhelmed the society could be curb if teachers who are currently on training would see teacher educators that would serve as role models to them. This would be the beginning of the sustainable transformation process yearned for to be transmitted to subsequent generation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are the suggestions supporting this study:

1. The university management should ensure that only corruption free persons are given appointive positions to begin value reorientation in the system.
2. Teacher educators should model what they teach their students in their worklife and lifestyle for immediate result in value reorientation process.
3. Teacher trainees should emulate good character and jettison the negative ones on display by their lecturers in order to have a better next generation.
4. The university management should ensure that erring teacher educators get commensurate punishment for their actions.
5. The government should put reward system in place for those who model true value reorientation to enjoy.

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